

Workshop - Inclusion of ethics in engineering education: “Ethic pills”

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Abstract

This proposal outlines a hands-on session, a revised iteration of a similar workshop presented at PAEE/ALE'2023. Despite broad consensus on the necessity of incorporating an ethical dimension into engineering studies, a dedicated course on engineering ethics is absent in many engineering degree programs. The proposed workshop aims to facilitate participants in exploring methodologies for integrating ethical considerations into existing courses, irrespective of the primary subject matter. The session will delve into strategies for selecting pertinent ethical topics, whether directly related to the course content or otherwise, and integrating them effectively within the course structure.

Keywords: Ethics in engineering; Ethics in engineering education; Active Learning.

1 Introduction

The promotion of reflection on ethical issues, alongside other generic competencies, is widely recognized as essential in the educational development of future engineers. A complete review about the relevant aspects of ethics in engineering education can be found in Chance et al. (2025). However, the emphasis on technical knowledge within many engineering curricula often limits the allocation of syllabus space for the specific cultivation of transverse competencies. The lack of dedicated space for ethics within technical courses represents a significant institutional barrier, as noted by researchers such as Walczak et al. (2010) and Davis (2006). Illustrative of this challenge, the Telecommunication Engineering degree at the University of Alicante includes “the ethical responsibility of engineering work” as a stated learning objective, yet lacks any compulsory or elective courses specifically addressing ethical issues. The study conducted by Walczak et al (2006) identified five prevalent obstacles to integrating ethics into engineering curricula:

- Curricular saturation limiting space for ethics education.
- Insufficient faculty training in teaching ethics.
- Lack of incentives for faculty to incorporate ethics.
- Inconsistent policies regarding academic dishonesty.
- Institutional growth straining existing resources.

The literature proposes various approaches for introducing ethics into engineering education, including a systematic framework presented by Li and Fu (2010).

Notably, findings from the Board of European Students of Technology Symposium (BEST, 2006) indicate a clear student demand for discussions on ethics and critical thinking within engineering education. The symposium also highlighted common challenges encountered when ethics courses are included in engineering programs:

- Talking about the inclusion of ethics in current university education there are different situations:
 - Complete specific course on ethics.
 - Integrated in some other courses – based on the will of the teachers or part of the program of the course.
 - The students are not taught ethics at all.

- Even if ethics is taught in some universities, like in the first two cases, it can be problematic in some situations:
 - The course is elective and not all the students are taking part because of the big number of courses they can choose.
 - The material is extensively theoretical.
 - Professors have no proper approach and make the course not attractive and tedious. The methods that are used are inappropriate.

Acknowledging student perspectives is crucial for designing effective and well-received ethics-related activities. Student suggestions often emphasize the need for:

- The course should give a direction of thinking that would make people more aware of their actions. By introducing a certain level of criticism, automatic behaviour would be excluded from decision making.
- Students generally would like to have interaction among all the students that enrolled the course and the teacher. It is a way through which more ideas could come up and more sharing could exist.
- The course should include case studies, examples from real life, problem-solving methods. The course should represent a lot of examples from real life.
- Dynamic course: as the time is changing the material should also change. The technologies are changing, so the courses should take it into account.
- About the people who will teach the course there were more ideas:
 - The person should have not just theoretical knowledge but also a practical background, the person should have experience as working as an engineer or as an option, special training on ethics.
 - Cooperation among two persons: engineer who will be practical and philosopher who will be theoretical.

Based on prior research involving engineering students at the University of Alicante, Table 1 presents topics frequently cited as desirable for inclusion in ethics sessions.

Table 1. Topics to be included according to students' opinion.

	Topic	%
1	Acting in accordance with personal principles	25
2	Social/environmental impact of work	22
3	Personal attitude (confidence, personality, commitment...)	13
4	Fair labour market/labour intrusiveness	10
5	Economic considerations	10
6	Professionalism	10
7	Other unclassified aspects	10

2 Activities

The primary objective of the hands-on session is to demonstrate practical methods for incorporating ethical considerations into any engineering course, aligning where possible with student preferences for such activities. Davis (2006) advocates for 'micro-insertion' as a technique to integrate ethics into technical courses minimally disruptively and in a manner valued by students. Furthermore, there is broad consensus, as highlighted by Harris et al. (1996), that case studies represent an optimal method for teaching professional ethics. Techniques such as "drawing the line" and analyzing conflict cases are effective modes for addressing ethical dilemmas within case studies. Participants will be organized into small, diverse groups to encourage varied perspectives. The session will introduce a methodology combining micro-insertion with case studies

(termed "ethic pills") for integrating ethics in contexts where dedicated courses are unavailable. The proposed session structure is as follows:

- Topic presentation.
- Warm-up activity.
- Group activities (ethics pills).
- Discussion.
- Conclusion.

3 Expected results

During the session, participants will engage with the proposed activities from a student perspective. The most significant insights are anticipated to emerge from the subsequent discussion phase. Feedback regarding the perceived utility of the proposed methodology and suggestions for enhancing its effectiveness and engagement will be particularly valuable.

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